

Oxidation of Esters by Bromine and *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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We wish to report some important features of the oxidation of esters by bromine and *N*-bromosuccinimide. This is the first kinetic report of the oxidation of esters by these oxidants and the procedure adopted is the same as reported by Venkatasubramanian and Thiagarajan in their work with alcohols.¹ Our earlier experiments to oxidize esters by V^v resulted only in the oxidation of alcohol, the cleaved product of the ester. The present experiments have been conducted in 100% acetic acid containing potassium acetate (0.15*M*) as buffer and of *pH* 3.5 at 60°. Under these conditions hydrolysis of ester does not take place and what is observed is oxidation of the ester and not that of the hydrolysed product, alcohol. Under these conditions the medium is quite stable which has been established by an independent run. The relative rates of oxidation of isopropanol and isopropyl acetate make this point amply clear. In addition it has been recently suggested by proton magnetic resonance studies² that hydrolysis does not occur under these *pH* conditions.

Rates were followed by iodometry and the reaction follows second order kinetics and depends upon the rate expression :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_2[\text{Ester}][\text{Bromine}]$$

The second order rate constants obtained with all esters are given below in Table I. The relative concentrations of ester to bromine were constant (1 : 1), and there is no bromination of the product formed. Some of the products have been identified and they are the corresponding carboxylic acids except in the case of benzyl esters where it is benzaldehyde that is formed. The procedure adopted is that of Graham and Westheimer³.

A parallel study by *N*-bromosuccinimide was also carried out to decide whether *N*-bromosuccinimide acts as a reservoir for bromine or oxidises the substrate directly. If it is the former, the rates should be identical with those obtained with bromine. It has been established in benzylic substitution that bromine and *N*-bromosuccinimide act alike as shown by the identical ρ values.⁴

We find that rates of *N*-bromosuccinimide oxidations carried out under these conditions are about half of the rates by bromine which seems to confirm a dual process as postulated by Venkatasubramanian and Thiagarajan (loc. cit.). The first stage of oxidation is presumed to be by *N*-bromosuccinimide and the second stage of oxidation by molecular

1. N. Venkatasubramanian and V. Thiagarajan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, **35**, 3349.
2. N. G. Deno and N. H. Potter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3555.
3. G. T. E. Graham and F. H. Westheimer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **80**, 3030.
4. R. E. Pearson and J. C. Martin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 354.

bromine (presumably with little competing oxidation by *N*-bromosuccinimide also) formed in the reaction because of accumulation of Br⁻ in the system. The rate constants for the first and second stages with *N*-bromosuccinimide are 2.0×10^{-3} and 5.0×10^{-3} respectively for ethyl acetate, and 2.3×10^{-3} and 3.9×10^{-3} respectively for isopropyl acetate.

TABLE I

Oxidant-Bromine, pH, 3.5, Temp. 60°

Substrate	$10^3 \times k_2$ l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Methyl acetate	3.2
Ethyl acetate	3.09
<i>n</i> -Propyl acetate	1.68
<i>iso</i> -Propyl acetate	3.22
<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate	2.51
Benzyl acetate	9.98
Benzyl benzoate	5.0
Ethyl benzoate	2.62
<i>iso</i> -Propanol	5976.0*

* Extrapolated from previous data (loc. cit.).

TABLE II

- (1) *Substrate*, (2) *Oxidation by NBS in presence of KBr*,
 (3) *Oxidation by NBS in presence of mercuric acetate*,
 (4) *Oxidation by NBS (first stage)*,
 (5) *Oxidation by Br₂*.

(1)	$10^3 \times k$ l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹			
	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Ethyl acetate	2.97	1.93	2.0	3.09
Benzyl acetate	10.00	5.31	5.2	9.98

Further, initial addition of potassium bromide to *N*-bromosuccinimide completely suppresses the first part of the reaction, and the reaction rate is similar to the second stage of the reaction or for bromine oxidation under identical conditions.

But we find the first stage of *N*-bromosuccinimide oxidation rates and the *N*-bromosuccinimide oxidation in presence of mercuric acetate are similar; this is probably due to the fixation of Br⁻ formed as unionized HgBr₂. There is no abnormal slowing down of the process as found in *iso*-propanol oxidation by Venkatasubramanian and Thiagarajan (loc. cit.).

The results (Table I) indicate that the benzylic system is attacked fastest in the series studied.